

Recommended citation: Ruijten, P. (2021). The value of interdisciplinary presentations for engineering students. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 1222-1228). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14651422.

The value of interdisciplinary presentations for engineering students

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Conference Key Areas: Attractiveness and future engineering skills.

Keywords: Communication, Presentations, Audience analysis, Future engineer

ABSTRACT

The engineer of the future is not only able to find innovative solutions to big problems, but also continues to learn about new topics that are relevant to these problems. They have a can-do mentality, are system thinkers, and are able to link their engineering background to relevant societal challenges. And most importantly, they work in multidisciplinary teams with engineers with diverse backgrounds. One aspect crucial to success is the engineer's ability to communicate with engineers with different backgrounds. Time and time again, projects get delayed or even fail because, for example, the software engineer did not fully understand the architect. In order to prevent this, students should be able to discuss and present their work in interdisciplinary settings. A project was run which had the main objective to create an environment in which students communicate about their (research) findings to peers with different backgrounds. The project was split into four phases: an exploration phase to gather information on how communication between students can be deployed in an interdisciplinary approach; a development phase in which a training for students and teachers was created; an intervention phase in which the training was applied and feedback from students was collected; and an evaluation phase designed to evaluate the intervention and provide recommendations to other departments and/or universities. This paper describes the steps of the project and ends with recommendations on how to apply the lessons learned in practice.

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1 INTRODUCTION

An important element that was introduced in many Bachelor programs globally are the so-called Professional Skills. These skills are intended to enable students to develop professional competencies that will help them in their future career. However, surveys consistently show that these skills are not sufficiently integrated in the educational programs. Bachelor students consistently rate such skills as insufficient. Alumni indicate that these skills are an important component of their jobs, but that they are insufficiently incorporated in their educational programs. Employees of alumni indicate a lack of communication and other skills, which manifests itself by the notion that a programmer and a designer working on the same project have difficulties communicating about this project. The Dutch minister of education indicated in an interview in *Trouw* on October 25 2019 that students experience a high pressure to perform, while the job market asks for very different qualities such as the ability to work in groups and to connect to others.

At the same time, intensive, challenge-based and project-based education is introduced in a multitude of educational programs [1–3]. This way of learning will prepare students better for their life after University, as it requires that students learn to give constructive feedback, work together in (interdisciplinary) teams, learn to communicate on an academic level, and learn how to plan for longer projects at an early stage in their educational programs. Efforts that allow students to work together with peers from different programs are successful, indicated by the high amount of attention towards [department]. At [department], students from different departments work together on projects with an applied focus. This approach allows students to learn how to communicate with those who have different backgrounds. The number of students who can participate in such programs is however limited, as most students will continue doing their final Bachelor projects in their own departments. If universities want to manifest themselves as enablers of interdisciplinary communication between students, other innovative solutions should be considered.

The notion that Professional Skills in general, and especially the ability to link different disciplines, should be a crucial element of higher education is also highlighted by Bert van der Zwaan [4], who argues that soft skills applied to a multidisciplinary context will play a defining role in teaching in higher education in 2040. This prediction fits well with the so-called T-shaped skills [5], which refers to the notion that engineers need to have both in-depth knowledge and expertise in their own domain (i.e. the vertical bar of the T) and the ability to collaborate across disciplines (i.e. the horizontal bar of the T). When it comes to the learning of new skills, students are more likely to learn when new ideas are presented. This helps them to have a fresh look on their own work as well [6], implying that that interdisciplinary presentations and discussions help students expand their knowledge and perspectives on their own topic. As such, providing the option for students to present in multidisciplinary settings enables them to learn more, and simultaneously it better prepares them for our future society.

In order to achieve this, students need to be given the right tools and support that helps them developing this new skill. This concept paper describes the steps that were taken to reach that goal. A project was defined and split into four phases. The first phase (exploration) was designed to gather information on how the existing communication skill can be adjusted into an interdisciplinary approach. The second phase (development) was designed to apply the knowledge gained in the first phase into a training program for students and teachers. The third phase (intervention) was designed to gain experience with the training program and collect some feedback from students that would help the further development. The fourth and final phase (evaluation) was designed to mainly evaluate how students experienced the intervention, and how we could further develop it in the near future.

2 EXPLORATION PHASE

The main goal of this phase was to gather information on how the existing communication skill could be adjusted into an interdisciplinary approach. To achieve this, two types of data were used: (1) Students who recently finished their Bachelor End Project were asked to complete a survey that tapped into their experiences with the final presentations, and how they could be altered to be given to an interdisciplinary audience, and (2) a co-design session was organized in which teaching support staff, experts from Education and Student Affairs, and students worked towards a description of the training program that had to be developed.

2.1 Survey responses

A total of 32 students (20 males, 12 females, age ranging from 20 to 26) completed the survey. The main outcome of the survey was that students do not necessarily feel that understanding of their domain knowledge is crucial for their presentation. This finding indicates that domain knowledge is not perceived as a very important criterion for giving a good presentation. This is an interesting finding, as we believe that communicating about the results one obtains in their domain to an interdisciplinary audience deepens their understanding of their own work. It could be seen as a way of active learning, which is shown to increase academic performance [7–9].

Important to note here is that the survey answers represent student perceptions of presentations that are given to an audience of peers who followed the same educational program. When asked what students would need from us to help them prepare for an interdisciplinary presentation, some provided very useful insights that can be categorized in three topics; (1) knowledge on what information is domain-specific and what is general knowledge, (2) balancing general and in-depth information such that people can follow the talk, and (3) a basic level of understanding of other disciplines. These three topics were further explored in a co-design session in which teaching support staff, educational experts, and students worked towards a description of the training program that had to be developed.

2.2 Co-design session

The co-design session took place on March 9 2020. The goal of the session was to collaboratively come up with some crucial points to make interdisciplinary presentations a success. When first asked to provide some points of improvement that could be taken into account when developing a training program for interdisciplinary presentations, two elements that were mentioned stood out: (1) there seems to be limited interaction with the audience in an average presentation, and (2) students are not concerned with doing an audience analysis and the target group is often unclear. From this we learned that this concept of an audience analysis may be key to the success of interdisciplinary presentations.

In terms of assessment, all attendees agreed that presentations should be assessed on both content and form, and separate assessors should be present for those two elements. A key factor in this is the question who will assess the content. This usually is an expert of the domain in which the student has done their work, but for multidisciplinary presentations this may require a different type of expertise. Both assessors should make use of their own rubric, where one focuses on the form of the presentation (e.g., language, posture, gestures, clarity, structure) and one on content (e.g., depth of the work, relation between the disciplines, original contribution).

The assessment of the audience analysis should be part of at least one of those rubrics. The participants of the session did not agree which of the rubrics that should be though. When doing a proper audience analysis, students should be capable of separating main and sub topics, provide sufficient depth for all audience members to understand the topic, while still not being

boring for domain experts. This connects best to the content of the presentation. On the other hand, a proper audience analysis also gives all audience members the feeling that they are being addressed properly, prevents extensive use of jargon, and makes the presentation come across as well-prepared. These elements fit better to the form of the presentation. This gave us the idea that an audience analysis should not be a separate part of any rubric, but should instead be incorporated in various elements in the rubrics for both content and form of presentations.

3 DEVELOPMENT PHASE

The main outcome of the exploration phase was that students could benefit from doing an audience analysis. We decided to develop and test a tool for this in a course in which students would already be presenting in front of an interdisciplinary audience. The audience analysis was presented to students as an a-priory inquiry of the kind of people who would be in the audience of their presentation, to help tailoring the presentation to those people. We decided to make students think about this topic by asking them to answer the following three questions: (i) what are the backgrounds of people in the audience for the upcoming presentation?, (ii) what are the roles of people in the audience?, and (iii) who are the three or so people that are most important for you to either convince about the quality of your work or to receive some feedback/input from and how will you achieve this?

We noticed that students struggled a bit with the third question, especially the last part of it. As they had never really thought about their presentations in this way, writing down how they would achieve their goals turned out to be difficult for them. Based on this, we decided to put some extra emphasis on this element during a workshop in which we zoomed in on their preparations for an interdisciplinary audience.

In this workshop, various topics related to giving a presentation in front of an audience with differing backgrounds were discussed. We decided to include three components in the workshop. The first was a short overview of the desired achievements in this project; giving students experience with interdisciplinary presentations, as this would prepare them better for the job market. The second was an overview of criteria that are included in all presentations, focused on the form of those presentations. Students should be familiar with these criteria, and giving them an overview would help refresh their memory. The third was the most important component; the additional audience analysis that would help students prepare for their interdisciplinary presentation.

4 INTERVENTION PHASE

This chapter describes our experiences with the workshop which was provided on 2 October 2020. The workshop had three main components: (i) background information on giving interdisciplinary presentations, (ii) a discussion on current criteria for presentations, and (iii) a discussion on extra criteria that play a role when presenting for a multidisciplinary audience.

4.1 Background information

We started by explaining the general aims of the current project. That is, we presented the notion that students tend to work in multidisciplinary teams after their graduation, that they also often need to present their work to various stakeholders, and that these presentations call for a different skill-set than the presentations they are used to giving. This part of the workshop is meant as an eye-opener and to attract the attention of students to the topic. Students were made to understand that a presentation in front of an audience of people with various backgrounds is conceptually different from any presentation they had given so far in

their program. Even though they did understand the importance of the topic, students did not yet fully grasp how they would go about preparing for an interdisciplinary presentation.

4.2 Discussion on current criteria

After this, we checked to what extent students were aware of the criteria that were used for evaluating the form of presentations. Students were able to mention most of them, although not in their official classification:

1. Quality of work delivered; focuses on content and explanations
2. Structure; focuses on primary versus secondary topics and goals
3. Interaction with audience; focuses on engagement of audience members
4. Non-verbal behavior; focuses on eye-contact, posture, and gesturing
5. Verbal behavior; focuses on fluency, language, volume, and pronunciation
6. Visual aids; focuses on balance between text and visuals

When asked to reflect on how well they scored on these criteria, students were mostly positive about their abilities, with an occasional exception. One observation was that students felt comfortable sharing their strong and weak points on these criteria. We believe this was enhanced by creating an informal atmosphere in which these elements were discussed, and that the workshop had a small-scale character as only 12 students participated in the course. We did not perform this workshop with a bigger group or on another (online) platform (yet), so it is hard to predict what will happen with such a bigger group.

4.3 Discussion on extra criteria

The discussion on extra criteria focused on elements that make a presentation for a multidisciplinary audience more complex than a regular presentation. Two distinct elements were highlighted. The first was that such a presentation requires the student to obtain knowledge that reaches further than that of their own discipline. It is important for students to understand the work their team members are doing if they want to present this to a multidisciplinary audience. Students indicated that a group project could not be performed if members of the group are not informed about what the others are doing. As these others were students with different backgrounds, this basic understanding of each others' work was perceived as more complicated compared to regular group projects with students from the same educational program.

The second element that was highlighted was the importance of doing an audience analysis. After doing an exercise on this, students indicated that they found it useful to think about who would be at the presentations, as this would also help them seeing the presentations from a different perspective than they had before. The exercise itself was not performed very well, though. Students had difficulties putting themselves in the perspective of different audience members, or trying to understand what those audience members would like to hear from them. Students were mostly wondering what to do to make members in their audience satisfied with their presentation. An important part of this discussion revolved around the question: if you would be [audience member], what would you expect to hear and see in this presentation? From this it easily became apparent that audience members could be categorized into clusters. People in the different clusters would expect different levels of complexity, detail, and background information from a presentation. Seeing this realization take place in the group of students was a good moment in the workshop, as this would help them prepare for their presentation.

We had expected that moderating the discussion between the students would be sufficient to

help them reach this conclusion, but a bit of nudging was needed to step away from seeing the audience as separate people but more as clusters that could be addressed separately. From this we learned that the assignment connected to the workshop could maybe do this nudging next time, and we would have to change the description of it in such a way that the roles that are mentioned with the second question more explicitly steer towards a classification of those roles, with specific criteria for the categories in which audience members can be clustered.

5 EVALUATION PHASE

This chapter presents the main outcomes of the student evaluation related to the interdisciplinary presentations throughout the project. It should be noted that in the student evaluations that were collected after the course, no specific questions were asked about the workshop on interdisciplinary presentations. Students of the course indicated that in general they enjoy learning from other disciplines, thinking about how to make their disciplinary knowledge valuable for the interdisciplinary projects, and working on open ended challenges. Even though these elements are positive, they do not necessarily provide clear information about how the specific activity in the course was experienced by the students. It is therefore important to include questions that are connected to specific activities in future instances of the course.

Nevertheless, many discussions have taken place between the coaches and the students shortly after the activity, and throughout those meetings, the following issues were raised by the students:

- Students asked many questions about levels of detail that should be included in their final presentations. This shows that they had internalized the notion of presenting for people with varying backgrounds, and wanted to verify whether the decisions they were making were the right ones.
- Students expressed concerns that the audience analysis made them drop too many details of the individual parts of the project, and that their academic coach would therefore not hear anything new in the presentations. This shows that they were trying to involve all members of the audience equally, and that they had difficulties doing so. This in turn is not unexpected, as it is the first time that students are involved in interdisciplinary presentations.
- Students indicated that they wanted to discuss details of their individual projects with their academic coaches before the final presentations. This would help them find out which elements were crucial to include in their presentations, and which details could be omitted. This shows that students understood that not all technical details should be included when presenting for a multidisciplinary audience, but a certain level of expertise was still expected to be shown.
- Students were more keen to perform stakeholder analyses prior to other presentations. This shows that they were working out what the goals and ambitions of different stakeholders in the projects were while they were preparing for further presentations. This in turn could be interpreted as a way for students to try to understand their audience and tailor their presentations to that audience.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The outcomes of the project are promising, as it has given us clear insights on how to create an environment in which students can communicate about their (research) findings to peers with different backgrounds. The main three takeaways from the project are described below:

1. When students are to present their work in front of an interdisciplinary audience, the

best way to prepare them for this is making them perform an audience analysis. Making them think about who will be in the audience, clustering the different roles that the audience members have, and tailoring the story to people in those different clusters, enables students to present their story in an understandable manner to all members of the audience.

2. Assessment of presentations that students give in front of an interdisciplinary audience should focus on both form and content, and the audience analysis element should not be a separate element of the assessment forms (rubrics). Instead, the outcomes of a successful audience analysis should show in the other components, as for example the structure of the presentation (a form element) will become better when a proper audience analysis has been performed. At the same time, students will show a better understanding of their own work, due to the meta-cognitive skills that are acquired while preparing for the presentation.
3. These outcomes link to an essential skill of learning. When students present about their work in front of an audience of their peers, they stay within their little box. The knowledge they obtain throughout their educational however, career needs to be fitted in a larger network. Analyzing an interdisciplinary audience and connecting ones own disciplinary work to that audience provides opportunities for doing exactly that, showing the value of interdisciplinary presentations for engineering students.

References

- [1] Marie Magnell and Anna-Karin Högfeldt. *Guide to challenge driven education*. KTH Royal Institute of Technology, 2015.
- [2] Geoff Mulgan, Oscar Townsley, and Adam Price. *The challenge-driven university: how real-life problems can fuel learning*, 2016.
- [3] Scooter Willis, Greg Byrd, and Brian David Johnson. Challenge-based learning. *Computer*, 50(7):13–16, 2017.
- [4] Bert Van der Zwaan. *Higher education in 2040. A global approach*. Amsterdam University Press, 2017.
- [5] Thomas Kelley. *The ten faces of innovation: IDEO's strategies for beating the devil's advocate & driving creativity throughout your organization*. Crown business, 2005.
- [6] Adrianna Kezar. Understanding sensemaking/sensegiving in transformational change processes from the bottom up. *Higher education*, 65(6):761–780, 2013.
- [7] Henk Vos and Erik de Graaff. Developing metacognition: a basis for active learning. *European journal of engineering education*, 29(4):543–548, 2004.
- [8] Kyoungna Kim, Priya Sharma, Susan M Land, and Kevin P Furlong. Effects of active learning on enhancing student critical thinking in an undergraduate general science course. *Innovative Higher Education*, 38(3):223–235, 2013.
- [9] Scott Freeman, Sarah L Eddy, Miles McDonough, Michelle K Smith, Nnadozie Okoroafor, Hannah Jordt, and Mary Pat Wenderoth. Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(23):8410–8415, 2014.